

DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT OF HYBRID COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The damage development in interply hybrid composites consisting of high tensile graphite fiber HTA7/ Narmco 5245 layers and high modulus graphite fiber HM45 and the same matrix material under tensile static and fatigue loading was compared to that in laminates made of pure HT or HM fibers with the same layup. Some specimens were barely visible impact damaged before testing. Acoustic emission measurements, quantification of the ultrasonic scans as well as X-ray pictures show that the damage development of hybrid laminates is mainly influenced through the HM layers.

KEYWORDS: Hybrids; Fatigue; Nondestructive Testing; Delamination; Edge Effect

1. INTRODUCTION

Hybridization with more than one type of fiber in the same matrix offers unique features that can be used to meet diverse design requirements in different industrial applications. In the literature (for example: 1-7) many authors are concerned with hybridization of composites with different fibers, e. g., glass, aramid, graphite; other publications are related to intraply hybrids (8, 9), but, investigation of hybrids with fibers of the same material are rare (10).

The present paper reports over an experimental work conducted to study the damage development under static and fatigue tensile loading in hybrid laminates consisting of two different type of graphite fibers, i.e. HT and HM, compared to laminates consisting of only HT or HM fibers. Results obtained from NDT methods like AE, US, and X-ray used to monitor the damage progression are presented.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials and Specimen Configuration The materials used in this ongoing investigation were HTA7 and HM45 carbon fibres in a Narmco 5245 epoxy resin. The

laminate lay-up consisted of 47% 0° layers, 47% $\pm 45^\circ$ layers and 6% 90° layers, with a total of 17 layers. The hybrid laminates had the $\pm 45^\circ$ layers from HM45 material. For comparison purposes laminates with only HTA7 and only HM45 fibers having the same lay-up were fabricated by Dornier and also tested.

Specimens of dimensions 170mm by 50mm were cut from the 2mm panels after impact damage and were fitted with GFRP tabs. The barely visible impact damage (BVID) was introduced in a drop weight test facility with the following parameters: hemispherical steel impactor with a diameter of 10 mm, a mass of 300 g and a drop height of 1m. The plates were clamped between two steel plates with a hole of 20 mm diameter.

2.2 Mechanical Tests The static and fatigue tensile tests were performed on a Schenk servo-controlled hydraulic test machine. For the fatigue tests it was load-controlled at constant amplitude with harmonic axial loading at a frequency of 4 Hz. The load level was chosen in such a way that an evident damage propagation was noticeable with the help of US-scanning

2.3 Damage Monitoring Techniques The damage that occurred during static loading was monitored by acoustic emission equipment from Physical Acoustics (PAC 3400) with a 150 kHz transducer. During fatigue loading the ultrasonic-in situ (USIS) method developed in our institute (11) was used to evaluate the degree of damage progression. USIS allows the US inspection of specimens without removing them from the loading frame and avoids the immersion in a water tank, a procedure which can lead to misinterpretation of US measurements (12). This way of doing the US inspection avoids, firstly, the problem encountered with small misalignments of the specimens which can cause a change in the direction of damage progression by clamping the specimen again after each US-inspection, and secondly, it is time saving. The ultrasonic equipment used was a Krautkrämer KB6000, a selfmade scanning mechanism, Fig. 1, and an IBM PC for data management. The results of the US pulse echo measurement are the standard C-scan and the H-scan. H-scan, which shows the isohypsi, lines connecting areas of equal rear-wall echo (RE) amplitude, offers the possibility to quantify the damage development in the specimen. To monitor the damage development during fatigue loading and find the confirmation of the AE-measurements under static loading, penetrant-enhanced X-ray radiography (Seifert-Isovolt 60) was also used.

3. TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Tensile Static Tests The damage caused in composite laminates under BVID conditions can be quantified through determining the mean value of all measured US-RE amplitudes, U_i , over the scanned area of the specimens. Results obtained for the different laminates are presented in Fig. 2, as a per cent of the intact specimens. All 3 laminates, high tensile, high modulus as well as the hybrid laminate show similar decrease of the US mean value, but the difference between them, is not significant. Fig.3 shows the change of the mean acoustic energy over the applied tensile stress. The mean acoustic energy was obtained through summation of the event energy of all events divided by the number of events. All laminates show a steady increase of the mean AE-energy with higher tensile loads. The

measured points for hybrid and HM laminates show the same tendency, pointing out that the damage mechanism of the hybrid laminate is mainly controlled through the HM layers. HT laminates show lower mean AE-energies because up to this loading stage not so many events with higher energy level occurred. Proof of this behaviour can be seen in Fig. 4 where the X-ray picture shows specimens after tensile loading of HT (654 MPa), HM(568 MPa) and hybrid laminate (486 MPa). The HT specimen shows cracks confined to the impact damaged area. The HM specimen shows a higher degree of damage in the impacted area and also cracks running along the outer 0° layers. The damage in the hybrid laminate is intermediate to that observed in the HT and HM laminates.

3.2 Damage Development in Fatigue The quantification of the damage development in the specimens under tensile fatigue loading is possible by means of calculating the US-RE-mean value related to the mean value of the virgin specimen, or the RE-mean value of the scanned area at the beginning of the test. Fig. 5 shows the behaviour of RE-mean values for undamaged and impact damaged specimens under fatigue loading. All specimens were tensile fatigue loaded at 600 MPa up to 10000 load cycles. The US-mean values decrease with increasing number of cycles for the different laminates due to various effects like matrix degradation, cracks in the layers as well as delamination. The curves for HT laminates with and without impact damage are almost parallel at the investigated load level, meaning that there was no significant increase of the impact damaged area. HM and hybrid laminates curves show a larger decrease in the US-RE-mean value, this means that the deterioration of the laminates are more severe, here again, the impact damaged area does not increase under the given load conditions. The deterioration of both laminates, i.e. HM and hybrid is mainly due to the stacking sequence of the layup. The free edge effect is predominant and causes the delamination at the edges. This delamination progresses faster than the impact delamination under tensile fatigue loading does. Fig. 6 shows a H-scan of a hybrid specimen after 5000 load cycles, here the dark areas are the regions where delamination took place, grey areas are regions where the damage would progress by further loading, white areas are regions where the specimen had experienced no damage since fatigue loading was imposed. Fig. 7 shows an X-ray picture for the different laminates after a fatigue load of 10000 cycles. HT laminates don't show any big change, contrary to HM laminates where partial delamination of the outer 0° as well as beginning of edge delamination is visible. The hybrid specimen shows clearly the edge delamination enlargement and the delamination of a 0° layer in the region of the impact damage. In this specimen the cracks of the 90° layer are also evident. HT and HM specimens do also have cracks in the 90° layer but they are not clearly visible in the picture.

Subsequent local US-investigations with the US probe placed near the impact damage confirm the damage development observed previously. Fig. 8 shows the curves obtained from the least square method of the US-RE-amplitude measurements done continuously over the period of 10000 cycles. HT specimens show again the least decrease of the RE-amplitude, meaning less deterioration than in the case of HM and hybrid laminates. Here again the hybrid laminate is the one with the highest degradation.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Three different laminates consisting of different graphite fibers were tested.. The impact damage induced in the specimens is almost the same in all laminates.The AE-energy results show that under static tensile loading the failure in hybrids is induced primarily through the HM-graphite fibres. Under tensile fatigue loading hybrid specimens show the largest damage propagation compared to specimens made out of pure HT or HM graphite fibres.

5. REFERENCES

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Figure 1. US-in situ: scanner

Figure 2. Mean value of US-RE amplitudes

Figure 3. Mean AE-energy of events for static loaded specimens

Figure 4. X-ray pictures after static tensile loading (from left: HT, HM and hybrid)

Figure 5. Behavior of US-RE-mean value for undamaged and impact damaged specimens under tensile fatigue loading

Figure 6. US-H-scan pictures at the beginning and after 1000 load cycles of a hybrid specimen. Legend: US-RE-amplitude in %.

Figure 7. X-ray picture of impact damaged specimens after 10000 load cycles
(from left: HT, HM and hybrid)

Figure 8. Development of US-RE-amplitude over fatigue loading cycles near the impact damaged area